

Magee Marsh Project, Ottawa County (41.60535, -83.15250)

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient benefit of the Magee Marsh Project has been limited due to tradeoffs in management goals. Water level management at this Project prioritizes seasonal wildlife habitat needs, generally flooding the wetland pool in the fall and draining it in the spring. However, for optimal nutrient retention, it may be more beneficial to fill the wetland pool in the spring, when there are larger nutrient runoff loads in the source creek water. Additionally, in both 2024 and 2023, the Project was kept isolated from the source creek water and drained for infrastructure improvements throughout the wetland complex. In 2024, the Project received water only once for a period of 10 days (a total of 149 million liters) and retained 0.2 lbs of phosphorus per acre.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is actively managed and has one distinct feature: a large (~ 170 acre) wetland pool that is connected to the adjacent Turtle Creek in two locations. Water enters from Turtle Creek at the western portion of the pool via one water level control structure (WLCS) and exits at the eastern portion of the pool via another WLCS. In the northwestern portion of the pool, a third WLCS allows water to flow into a canal to the north where it can then flow into a non-H2Ohio pool or Turtle Creek. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an adjustment of a WLCS that alters water flow speed and/or direction into or out of the wetland pool.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar coastal wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future Project site selection:

- Promote more frequent filling events in spring, when nutrient sequestration is most impactful for preventing harmful algal blooms in nearby Lake Erie.

As construction within the Project concludes and typical management activities resume, different nutrient retention patterns may emerge, though the tradeoffs between habitat- and nutrient-driven water level management will remain. More accurate nutrient retention estimates for future years can be facilitated by prompt notification of WLCS actions allowing timely sampling of hydrologic events, as well as information on the fate of pumped water.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.